

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Automatic Discrimination of Domestic Cat Sounds and Imitations

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September 2019

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Dedication

This study is dedicated to my beloved cousin Can Ozkan. You left the grace of the music on my life. Also, My cat Murphy, I can't love any cat else as much as I love you. I will always remember you both.

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Abstract

This study presents the results of automatic discrimination to distinguish the sounds of domestic cats and the sounds of domestic cats imitated by humans. In this work, our main contribution is domestic cat sound imitation data set creation and investigation of classification accuracy both between original cat sounds and imitations mutually. First, we analyzed the specific types of vocalization of cats, which are the main representatives of the cat sound categories. Then, we use Freesound to create a data set of these specific type of cat sounds vocalizations. We created an imitation data set consisting of the vocalizations of the humans precisely for the same categories. We use Librosa to extract the features of these new data sets, and Weka to distinguish cat sounds from their imitations by using machine learning techniques.

Keywords: Cat Sound Classification, Cat Sound Imitation, Imitation Dataset

Chapter 1

Introduction

In our first chapter, we present an introduction to our research. We begin with discussing diversified studies consisting of animal species following domestic cat vocalizations. Then, we summarize the goals and contributions of this thesis.

1.1 Animal Sound Classification

Voice is a substantial communication tool for not only humans but also other creatures in the world. As we express ourselves in different words, they do so with different vocal techniques with different timbres. Animal sounds have been studied in many different fields. In 2006, a set of novel time-based audio descriptors first were introduced and their quality compared to other popular features by using birds, cats, cows, and dogs sounds.[1] Harma and Somervuo introduced a computationally efficient technique to classify sinusoidal representations of brief segments of bird song in 2004.[2] Again about birds, Dan Stowell, and Mark D. Plumbley introduce a technique for feature learning from large volumes of bird sound recordings in 2014.[3] In 2008, automatic frog sound identification system was developed.[4] Another research which has done by using frog sound is a classification method of animal species based on their sound signal which has been proposed by Jedol Dayou et al.[5] Moreover, A number of studies have been carried out to classify marine animals: Frstrup and Watkins discriminate marine animal sound variation into bi-

ological classes of signals to identify species, to quantify the repertoire of a single species, and to identify individuals.[6] The 500-vocalization data set was from two killer whales used in Murray et al. to classify the vocalizations by neural networks.[7] As well, to measure the similarity of whale sound using the same technique for the discrimination of frequency contours has been studied.[8] As seen in the above examples, animal sounds are used for different purposes in many studies together or alone, in order to examine and classify them in depth.

1.2 Domestic Cat Sound Vocalization

Domestic cats can deliver many messages to human beings through their voice generating capability. There are several studies in which cat vocalizations have been studied through acoustic analysis[9], comparison between feral cats and domestic cats[10], spectral characteristics of meows[11], general human capacity to identify sounds made by cats[12], visual classifications [13] and human perception of emotions from domestic cat vocalisations[14]. However, there is a surprisingly small number of papers specifically devoted to the classification of cat vocalizations. In this study, we focused on the discrimination of cat sounds from their imitations, which will be discussed in the following section.

1.3 Goals and Structure of the Thesis

The major motivation of this study is the personal interest in cats and lack of the number of studies concerning them. Secondly, as collaborative databases such as Freesound became widespread, various tools and methods for organizing them began to develop such as query by imitation. In these collaborative databases, ground truth is constituted by human annotators. Some imitations are very realistic, and people are fallible. Not only when annotating cat sounds, but also annotating other sounds in Freesound is possible to encounter many imitations. This study in the future could help query by imitation technique to minimize adding the false negatives to the output, especially in cat sound class.

In terms of collecting data efficiently, in this study, cat sounds are preferred since it is a well-known domestic animal, and their sub-categories are easy to understand. It is possible to imitate a cat sound in more than one way even though we consider only one specific sub-category. Therefore, having too many imitations for a single category can contribute to the accuracy in such experiments. That is why we use sub-categories of the cat vocalizations in our experiments. Moreover, the existing cat datasets have background noise which prevent to have reliable and accurate test results. Therefore, we design two new datasets for automatic classification purposes in the context of cat sounds. The first is the cleanse of specific cat categories from Freesound, and the second is the creation of a sound imitation dataset in the corresponding categories and amounts. In this study, we aim to contribute to automatic classification of cat sounds research in two ways: discriminating original cat sound recordings from their human imitations relying on multiple machine learning methods, and creation of a new cat sound imitation dataset which can be used by other researchers to carry out further work on the topic.

Chapter 2

Related Work

We consider assembling the features used in previous works to gain better information about the characteristics of Cat sounds which will best fit discrimination scenario. In this Section, previous literature on the animal sound classification subject and created cat and imitation datasets will be discussed.

2.1 Cat Sound Classification

To properly classify the cat sounds, accurate identification is necessary. One of the first papers exclusively devoted to the phonetic properties of cats' voices were first described by Moelk in 1944.[15] The focus of the paper is the identification of different kinds of cat vocalizations. It has been shown that the vocalizations of cats differ acoustically depending on how the sound was produced. The vocal sounds in cats can be divided into three main classes related to the mouth positions of the cat:

1. Sounds produced with the mouth close,
2. Sounds produced when the mouth is opened,
3. Sounds produced when the mouth is held tensely open in one position.

Table 1: The number of vocalisation types and sub-types identified

Vocalisation type	Subtypes
Meow	Mew, Squeak, Moan, Meow, Trill-meow
Purr	-
Trill	Chirrup, Grunt, Trill-meow
Howl	Howl, Howl-growl
Growl	Growl, Howl-growl
Hiss	Hiss, Spit
Snarl	-
Chirp	Chirp, Chatter

Based on the previous researches on acoustic characteristics of cat vocalizations, a detailed phonetic typology of domestic cat vocalizations presented by Schotz et al.[16]

Most of the sounds made by cats are divided into three groups; when they greet us, the murmurs(purr) or small squeaks are the sounds they make when they are feared or full of emotions (e.g., growling, hissing, spitting) and meow sound. Cats may produce very different kind of the meow sound depending on the cases.[17] Table 1 [16], shows the cat vocalization types and sub-types, which has been investigated so far in the literature.

2.2 Automatic Classification of Cat Sounds

Very little research has been done, especially in the field of classification of domestic cat sounds. One of the most comprehensive studies on cat sound classification was done by Pandeya and Lee.[18] In total, they collected 300 samples for every ten classes that they formed which are angry, defense, fighting, happy, hunting-mind, mating, mother-call, paining, resting, warning by using semantic explanations. They use transfer learning to extract features and use the Million Song data set to train the model. Extracted features are grouped in 6 categories, including ensemble classifier method with predicted classifier results. Another study which has been done by Nicastro and Owren to classify meow sounds.[19] However, instead of using artificial intelligence, they examine the case with human participants to classify meow sounds. Likewise, a visual classification scheme for cat vocalizations is developed

and the spectrograms obtained from the recordings. Then, they identified three main characteristics, such as tonal, pulse, and broadband of cat vocalization, which then break down these categories in eight subcategories.[13]

2.3 Cat Imitation Datasets

So far, there has not been a study of imitation of cat sounds in particular, but various studies on imitation include cat sounds categories. VocalSketch data set v1.0.4 was constituted in 2015.[20] Data set contains thousands of vocal imitations in four categories: acoustic instruments(40), commercial synthesizers(40), every day (120), and single synthesizer(10). In these 4 different concepts, there are several imitations from 20 to 40 samples from different people. Hence the data set is so comprehensive, there are not many examples specifically for each category. In this dataset, there are 21 imitations of cat sounds. Yet another imitation data set is Vocal Imitation Data Set, which consists of 302 different categories from the AudioSet sound event ontology[21] and has 2,985 of original recordings.[22] Vocal Imitation Data set was rated by a human listener and 5,601 imitations that passed the quality check alongside 5,642 of recordings include drafts, training recordings and excluded ones during the quality assessment. Table 2 shows the categories, number of classes, listener-vetted imitations, and original recordings in Vocal Imitation Data Set[23]. As shown in the table, it has 31 categories for animals. Cat category has 173 imitations in total, four subcategories such as growling, hiss, meow, and purr. These categories collected using the class name as the search key from Freesound, which organized in a hierarchy based on the AudioSet Ontology will be used as the main data set for cat categories in this study.[24] The goal of Vocal Imitation Data Set is providing a clear pair of imitations that corresponds to reference sounds. Although this dataset has a sufficient amount of categories, as with other datasets, the number of cat sounds is too little to do a study on cat sound. Last but not least, the data set which has been created in Blancas and Janer's study, consist of 4 classes, including Cat, Dog, Car, and Drums. The classes and subcategories were chosen from Freesound according to their acoustic varieties, availability of examples and conceptual differences.[25]

Table 2: Categories in Vocal Imitation Set.

Categories	Classes	Imitations	Original Rec.
Animal	31	587	308
Channel, environment and background	4	74	40
Human sounds	38	714	375
Music	65	1247	646
Natural sounds	10	177	100
Sounds of things	134	2448	1316
Source-ambiguous sounds	20	354	200
Total	302	5601	2985

For the Cat category meowing, purring and yelling are selected as subcategories. The goal of their work is to analyze the signal description of human voice imitating, having a perspective about the capabilities of the human voice. In the end, they had 90.20% Accuracy for the tagged imitations Cat sound category with SVM classification algorithm. Although very few results appear to be generated by a very specific search, it should be said that Freesound[26] returns a number of false positive sounds by default, especially due to the similarity of the user-generated labeling system and the pre-calculated signal.[25] Such as, the Freesound cat category returns 208 results with the normal text-query method, while the technique developed by Blancas and Janer returns five narrowed results. The Freesound method may return false-negatives to the output however, five corresponded sound is also very few. Besides, Freesound has many imitation sounds which have not been labeled with imitation text which belie the users who need sounds in some specific categories. For these reasons, we decided to create an imitation dataset and clean the Freesound Cat sounds, which will be discussed in the next chapter.

Chapter 3

Methods and Materials

In this chapter, we present the datasets, toolboxes, and the extracted features used in our experiments. We start with an introduction to the datasets and continue with the information regarding toolboxes we utilize. After, the feature selection step and the decisions on each level of the experiments are explained.

3.1 Datasets

Animal sounds are one of the top-level category in Freesound Datasets[26], which is a platform for the collaborative creation of open audio collections labeled by humans. Freesound Datasets now is called Freesound Annotator. In this study will be using Freesound Datasets to obtain Cat Sounds and imitators that produce imitations to compose Cat Sounds Database.

3.1.1 Freesound Dataset (Cat Sounds)

Freesound Datasets under the new name Freesound Annotator has a collection of over 600 sound classes which have supplied with 297.144 audio samples. By the time the total number of contributors 468. Freesound has 448 audio samples for the Cat category including subcategories, which are Growling, Hiss, Cat communication, Purr, and Caterwaul, as shown in Figure 1.

FSD → Cat	
Hierarchy	🌳 > Animal > Domestic animals, pets > Cat
Description	Sounds associated with the familiar, furry, domestic carnivorous mammal.
URI	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cat
Siblings	Dog
Direct children	Growling Hiss Meow Cat communication Purr Caterwaul
Examples	
# audio samples	448
# ground truth	532 (propagated from children: 348)

Figure 1: Freesound Annotator web page for cat sound category.

According to the mouth positions which has been studied[15] and the availability of multiple examples of the sounds for each category, we decided to conduct experiments with three main subcategories. In total, we downloaded 267 samples for Meow category, 189 samples for Purr category, and 111 samples for Growling category from Freesound Datasets on 12Th of April, 2019. These samples are the most relevant ones which belong to the Freesound dataset ground truth. Ground truth covers two categories, called PP and PNP. PP means that the sound type is isolated from other sound types or with low background noise. PNP indicates that the sound clip contains different kinds of sounds alone or together with background sounds as a hiss.[24] Here, the biggest problem that we encounter is after downloading cat sounds, PNP category included in the ground truth as well as PP categories. So the cats' sounds which belong to different categories occur in the same record. To create categories that are unique to the class names, we have listened to all recordings one by one and split the cat sounds in different files to these correspond to a single category. The ones which carry a meaningful part from the other categories are considered as a new sound file and added to the relevant category. As a result of the fragmentation of sounds carrying more than one meaningful cat sound and removal of the parts that are not related to cats, 113 growlings, 567 meows (315

PP, 252 PNP), 273 purrs obtained. Since the growling category has many mothers hierarchically such as dog, big cat, wolves, after cleaning only 11 growling sound was decided as belong to the sounds of cats. Nevertheless, with the support of other split categories which contains growling sound, it reached 113 number of samples. In total, the number of cat sounds after cleaning and splitting reached 953 samples, including meow, purr, and growling.

Figure 2: Distribution of Purr Cat Class

Figure 3: Duration Distribution of the categories except Cat Purr Sound

The duration of the clips for the purr category are very long as seen in Figure 2 compare to the other categories. To create a more balanced dataset and since the

rest of the categories has a 10-second maximum duration as shown in Figure 3; we consider only the first 10 seconds of the Purr category. The sounds are listened one by one to be sure that they have only purr sound in the beginning.

3.1.2 Cat Sound Imitation Dataset Creation

22 individuals have participated in the experiment sessions. A repository link was given to the participants which have created with Github.[27] In this repository, the experiment purposes and the directions to record cat imitation sounds explained. In the web site, there were three main steps for the participants:

- Reading the instructors on the right side of the page(Figure 4)
- Listen to the example sounds to understand better what to imitate
- Record the imitations in a quiet environment and send by email

Figure 4: Domestic Cat Sound Imitation Repository Instructors

The same method used as in [23] and [25] by giving an example sounds to the participants. For each subcategory, a series of cat sounds from Freesound combined

and added to the repository as reference sounds. (Figure 5)

Meow

The classic tonal communication sound made by cats.

▶ 0:00 / 0:28 ● —▶ 🔊 ⋮

Purr

A tonal fluttering sound made by cats to indicate contentment or relaxed pleasure.

▶ 0:00 / 0:22 ● —▶ 🔊 ⋮

Growling

A low, guttural vocalization produced by animals as a warning, a sign of aggression, or to express anger.

▶ 0:00 / 0:43 ● —▶ 🔊 ⋮

Please fill the form **after** you record the imitations!

Name and Surname:

Email:

Age:

Which category is the most difficult to imitate? ▼

Which category is the easiest to imitate? ▼

Do you have cats or have you ever lived with cats? Yes No

Please select your gender: ▼

Figure 5: Domestic Cat Sound Imitation Repository Given Reference Sounds and Participant Survey

Since the sounds in the Freesound are diverse in terms of recording quality, no instructions were given to the participants about the environment that the records should be recorded on. So the decision is left to the user to have the same amount of diversity. Furthermore, imitators were asked if they have pets in their homes and how old they are, as same as in study [25]. Additionally, we added gender to be able to measure the accuracy of different sexes and the most challenging and easiest category rating. All recordings transferred to a computer, and WAV audio files (44.1 kHz, 16 bit, mono) extracted.

According to the feedback from the users, they found the experience entertaining. Notwithstanding, many of the participants found the experiment tough and gave up. All in all, total number of samples collected in consequence of the experiment is in Table 3. These are the final numbers after poor quality or unrelated sounds removed. For instance, excessive wind noise in the microphone, hissing imitations

Table 3: Number of Cat Sounds and Imitations

Sub Categories	Number of Collected Imitations	Freesound Cat Sounds	
		Original size	Size After Modification
Meow	263	260	567
Purr	255	189	273
Growling	222	11	113

in the growling category, etc.

3.2 Toolboxes

In this section, we present the toolboxes used in the extraction of features, selecting of the features, and automatic classification of our experiments. Detailed information on these steps provided in Section 3.3.

Librosa

LibROSA[28] is a Python package for music and audio analysis. Provides the building blocks needed to create music information retrieval systems. In our study, we use LibROSA’s I/O functionality and feature extraction functions to extract spectral features.

Weka

Weka[29] is a toolbox with a wide range of machine learning algorithms Which includes tools for data preprocessing, classification, and visualization. Published under the GNU General Public License and written in Java.

Audacity

Audacity[30] is a Free, audio editor and recording application software developed by a group of volunteers as open source. For this work Audacity’s 2.3.1 version and editing features are used to edit datasets.

3.3 Proposed Method

Our proposed method follows a supervised classification approach, which is commonly used in many Music Information Retrieval (MIR) tasks. Figure 6 presents the steps of our plan.

Figure 6: The Flow of Study

3.3.1 Feature Extraction

Features are extracted with LibROSA[28] package. Although the actual cat sounds and imitations have not been studied together before, we used the features studied before to classify cat sounds and the features extracted to classify imitations which has been used in previous studies. Besides, we proposed some new features to see the most accurate ones and to know in which cases we can distinguish better imitations. In this study we used 54 features in total: Pitch, Chroma STFT, Root Mean Square, Spectral Centroid, Spectral Bandwidth, Spectral Rolloff, Zero Crossing Rate, Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients(MFCC). Each feature's mean and variation has been calculated. An essential aspect of the feature extraction step is that in most cases, we use the default values for the parameters of the feature extraction algorithms found in the toolboxes we use. A parameter optimization step can be applied to algorithms to improve the performance of automatic classification, but our recommended method does not use such measures. In addition, different toolboxes have different applications for the same features, and our work we do not compare these alternatives.

Pitch

The Pitch depends on the frequency or how many times per second the particles vibrate. The distance between one wave and the next indicates the wavelength.

For all sounds that move at the same speed, high-frequency sounds have very close waves to each other. Low-frequency sounds have a greater distance between the individual waves. Since we are using cat sounds subcategories which have different frequency range, we use this feature. LibROSA piptrack implementation uses a parabolic interpolation method described by [31] to calculate the pitch. In [32], they use F0 feature to find out agnostic vocalization types in cats. Moreover, the mean fundamental frequency has been used to investigate the correlation between calls of cats with their respective body weights. [33]

Chroma STFT

The main idea of chroma features is to add all spectral information related to a particular pitch class into a single coefficient. Chromatic properties can be considered as a vital prerequisite for high-level semantic analysis, such as for chord recognition or harmonic similarity estimation. The feature vector is extracted from the magnitude spectrum using a short-time Fourier transform (STFT). By LibROSA chroma stft implementation normalized energy for each chroma bin at each frame is obtained. Chroma stft generally helps to analyze music whose pitches can be meaningfully categorized. In our work, we wanted to see if melodic characteristics are useful to discriminate cat sounds.

Root Mean Square

RMS is the average loudness of the waveform that takes into account all instances of loudness statistics in the waveform. The calculation of the RMS value from audio samples is faster since it does not require a STFT calculation. Since not all the cat sound subcategories and imitations will not have the same loudness average, we use this feature to see if this feature has an impact on discrimination.

Spectral Centroid

Spectral Centroid defines the center of mass of a sound where is located and is calculated as the weighted mean of the frequencies present in the sound and in terms of human perception it is often associated with the brightness of the sound.

If the frequencies in music are the same throughout then spectral centroid would be around a center, and if there are high frequencies at the end of sound, then the centroid would be towards its end. The center of mass of cat sounds are very various and may have different high-frequency locations, so we consider this feature to see if this feature has an impact.

Spectral Bandwidth

Spectral Bandwidth is the difference between the upper and lower frequencies as the width of the frequency band of signal around the center point of the spectrum in a continuous signal of frequencies. This feature will be used to considering each cat sounds category may have a different bandwidth. For example, growling sound is more discrete sound when purr is more continuous.

Spectral Roll-off

The spectral roll-off is the frequency below which a certain percentage of the total spectral energy, defined for each frame as the center frequency for a bin of the spectrogram, is at least roll percent (default 0.85) of the spectrum energy that contained in this bin or lower bins.

Zero-Crossing Rate

The zero crossing rate is the rate of sign changes with a signal. It indicates the number of times the signal changes value, from positive to negative and vice versa, divided by the total length of the frame. This feature has been used widely in both speech recognition and music information retrieval, so we consider it because we are working with human imitations besides cat sounds as well.

Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients(MFCC)

The Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) of a signal are small set of characteristics that accurately describe the general shape of a spectral envelope and are used primarily in the processing of audio signals. In MIR, it is often used to describe

Table 4: Attribute Evaluators and Search Methods

Attribute Evaluator	Search Method
Correlation Attribute Evaluation	Ranker
Correlation-based feature subset evaluator	Best First GreedyStepwise
Information Gain Based Feature Selection	Ranker
Learner Based Feature Selection	Best First GreedyStepwise

the timbre. MFCCs are used commonly as features in speech recognition systems. The MFCC values are not very robust in the presence of additive noise. Therefore, it is reasonable to normalize their values in speech recognition systems to reduce the impact of noise.

3.3.2 Feature Selection

The selection of feature subsets identifies and removes as much irrelevant and redundant information as possible. This reduces the dimensionality of the data and the processing time and increases the performance of the mining task, which allows the learning algorithms to work more quickly and efficiently. The selection of features aims to find a subset of characteristics that can describe the data for a learning task, or better than the original data set. In WEKA[29], different methods are available.

Since feature selection algorithms have not been used in cat sound classification studies before, we used both filter and wrapper methods to see which algorithm would work best for the data. Filter methods measure the relevance of features by their relationship with the dependent variable and wrapper methods measure the usefulness of a subset of feature by actually training a model on it. Our proposed method uses four different algorithms to be able to define the most accurate one. Three filter methods were chosen for attribute selection: correlation features evaluator, correlation-based feature subset evaluator, information gain based feature selection. One wrapper method was chosen called Learner Based Feature Selection with Best First and Greedy Stepwise search methods. Table 4 shows a summary of all the evaluators we used with the search methods.

The correlation method evaluates the worth of features by measuring the correlation between the features and the class. Subset evaluator which compares a subset with

another subset which already determined. If the new subset returns better results concerning evaluation, then the new subset named as the new best one as well the process continues until the condition achieved. Information based gain calculates an output for each variable. The values vary between 0 to 1, and the values which have a higher information gain are selected. Learner based feature selection is supported by WrapperSubsetEval Technique in Weka. The algorithm used in subset evaluation does not need to be the same algorithm as which is used to model the problem.[34] We use the decision tree method because it is fast to train and powerful.

3.3.3 Automatic Classification

The primary purpose of this research was not to measure the efficiency of the algorithms or not increasing the accuracy. The aim is to see which is the best method to discriminate these imitations from the original cat sounds. However, we wanted to see the results of different methods by using various algorithms. We applied four classification algorithms: K-Nearest Neighbors(Knn), Random Forest(RF), Support Vector Machines(SVM), Naive Bayes (NB) as studied in the previous cat classification literature. We perform all algorithms only for the first experiment; then we carry out further experiment considering only the algorithms that obtained the highest accuracy in the first experiment. We perform 6 experiment with different datasets. In every experiment, except experiment 6, we split the data as a training set (80 percent) and test set (20 percent). For the training, we also use 10-fold cross-validation. The algorithms with their accuracy percentage can be seen in the Results section.

Experiment 1

In the first experiment, we use Cat and Imitation categories together with their subcategories as MeowCat, PurrCat, GrowlingCat, MeowHuman, PurrHuman and GrowlingHuman. The goal is to see the most difficult scenario possible with six different labels, and the correlation between them.

Experiment 2

Secondly, We want to measure the accuracy in terms of Human and Imitation category without sub-categories. By this way, it is possible to see what is the best approach to discriminate the imitations.

Experiment 3

In the 3rd experiment, the decomposition success of the corresponding subcategories is calculated. Experiment pairs are MeowCat-MeowHuman, PurrCat-PurrHuman, GrowlingCat-GrowlingHuman. The higher the discrimination rate, the easier it is to distinguish these imitations from real cat sounds, on the contrary, when the discrimination rate is low, it is aimed to see how successfully the participants are imitating the actual cat voice.

Experiment 4

Experiment 4 is to measure the female-male vocalization imitation effect on discrimination accuracy. Gender distribution will be used to exposing the characteristics of the sound of the domestic cat and evaluate the capabilities of human imitation measure.

Experiment 5

Further, the susceptibility of the human voice to imitate cat species concerning the status of owning a cat will be investigated. The experiment only with the owner of the cats, has been performed to check the accuracy without subcategories. The question is to find out if cat owners are better imitators or not.

Experiment 6

The last experiment will be performed to have an insight of the imitation quality. The idea is to train the model with real cat sounds and test them on human imitations with subcategories. By this way, we see which category has more accurate imitations.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Experiment Results

4.1.1 Experiment 1

In the first experiment, we aimed to see the distribution of all categories together. We used four different algorithms and four feature selection techniques. The data set (113 samples) is split as 80 percent as training and 20 percent as a test. We applied 10-fold cross validation to train the model. We follow this rule for the next experiments. Knn gives the highest accuracy with correlation attribute evaluator with the 86.95% accuracy as shown in Table 5. Correctly predicted categories for purr sound is more than other ones.

Table 5: Experiment 1 Results

Algorithms	Accuracy
Knn	86.95
Random Forest	80.43
SVM	78.98
Naive Bayes	70.28

Figure 7: Experiment 1 Confusion Matrix Test Results for six labels

Table 6: Experiment 2 Algorithms and accuracy

Experiment 2	Accuracy
Knn	95.03
Random Forest	93.26
SVM	87.58

4.1.2 Experiment 2

In the second experiment, different from the first, instead of using six labels, they were grouped into two categories: imitation sounds and cat sounds to see what is the best approach to detect imitations. Knn classifier gives 95.03% discrimination accuracy for when we use two labels for the number of data we have is reducing so the accuracy increasing (Table 5). Therefore, to experiment 1 compared to experiment 2, we sub-sampled the data for human and imitation category to not to give a different number of samples in the experiments to avoid misleading results. By reason of the experiment has 113 number of samples meanwhile experiment 2 has 701 samples. In the end, we had 91% accuracy on the test set.

4.1.3 Experiment 3

When we examine the sounds in different pairs, this experiment aims to see if there is a relation between discrimination accuracy and the imitation difficulty. The clas-

Figure 8: Experiment 2 Confusion Matrix Test Results for Human and Imitation labels

Table 7: Experiment 3 Results

	Cat Meow Human Meow	Cat Purr Human Purr	Cat Growling Human Growling
KNN Accuracy %	95.28	98.03	91.3

sifier has more accuracy in identifying purr. In table 7, it has been shown the decomposition success of the corresponding subcategories with Knn algorithm.

We had a different amount of samples for each class since the original cat sound data which we obtained from Freesound does not have the same amount. Especially, growling category is half of the other categories which may have an impact on the results. For meow pair, classifier gives 95.28% accuracy, and for purr pair, the accuracy is 98.03%, and for the growling pair, the accuracy is 91.03%.

4.1.4 Experiment 4

If we consider the accuracy as high when the imitations are not decent then we can compare the female and male imitation accuracy to see in which case the accuracy is higher. In this experiment, the aim is to see if female and male imitations have an impact on accuracy. For the female class 293 sound clips used and for the male class 298 sound clips used. Data sub-sampled with Weka's spread sub-sample function and 80% of the data for training, 20% of the data for the test step is used. Accuracy of the male imitations is 94%, female imitations accuracy is 93%. The confusion matrix of the categories on test set can be seen in Figure 9 and 10.

Figure 9: Confusion Matrix of Female Imitation and Cat Categories

4.2 Experiment 5

The scope of this experiment to see if the cat owners have worse accuracy than imitators who are not cat owners in terms of misleading the machine. To be able to identify categories during imitation experiment, participants have been requested to answer this field in the survey. Cat owners are the ones who live with cats or the ones who have lived with a cat before, and not cat owners are the participants who do not live with a cat. According to the survey results, the cat imitations are grouped as Cat Owners and not Cat Owners.

Figure 10: Confusion Matrix of Male Imitation and Cat Categories

In the first part of the experiment, a csv file with the original cat sounds and with the imitations of the only cat owners provided to the Weka. Second, original cat sounds and not cat owners' results have been measured to be able to compare the accuracy. The accuracy is 97% for both classes, as shown in Figure 11. The number of samples used in the test set are not equal since we have more data from Cat Owners. The amount of data distribution will be discussed in Survey results in section 5.3.

Figure 11: Confusion Matrix of Cat Imitations by Cat Owners and Not Cat Owners

4.3 Experiment 6

In the last experiment, we trained the model with subcategories of real cat vocalizations than test it on the human imitations. The aim was to see how realistic the imitations are and to see the most successful imitation category. Since we do not split the original cat vocalization data set as training and test, we had more samples. However, we sub-sample data to have the same amount of data belong to each class. At the end, each class has 113 number of samples as in Experiment 1. Likewise, all the cat vocalizations considered in training set with the subcategories (Meow, Purr, Growling) and for each class we have 222 samples. The overall accuracy at the end of this experiment is 89% for the training set and 54% for the test set. Figure 12 shows the confusion matrix of the test set.

Figure 12: Human Imitations test set results on confusion matrix that is trained on Cat Vocalizations

4.4 Survey Results

As mentioned in section 3.1.2, 22 participants involved in the experiment, and a link were given them to follow the experiment steps. One of these steps was filling a short form which requests information from the participants. They have been asked which is the most difficult category to imitate, which is the easiest to imitate, are

they lived with cats before and what is the gender of the participant.

Figure 13: Easiest Category Rating

The easiest and the most difficult categories have been asked to be able to compare imitation difficulty with the results. If a category is tough to imitate, participants might not create a good imitation which can affect the results. The percentage of the participant voting results can be found in Figure 13 and Figure 14. In the confusion matrix of Experiment 1 (Figure 7) this can be seen very clearly, and classifier has better accuracy for purr category. Likewise, growling category follows Purr with the second-highest discrimination.

Figure 14: Difficult Category Rating

Gender has been asked for experiment 4, which compares the female-male imitation

effect on discrimination accuracy (Figure 15), which we investigate if this gender characteristic has an impact on the imitation accuracy. The number of male and female participants are close so we can say that we have a balanced data in terms of gender. The results of Experiment 4 can be seen in the discussion part.

Gender Distribution in Experiment 4

Figure 15: Gender Distribution

Another information which has been asked to the participants is if they have a cat or have not. We assume that if a participant has a cat, they can create better imitations since they are more used to cat sounds. However, the information having a cat or not having a cat has been used in experiment 5, and we saw that accuracy is the same for both classes. Distribution of the participants who live with cats and who does not have cat can be seen in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Percentage of the participants who live with cats and who does not live with cats

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusion

In the last chapter of the thesis, our primary goal is to give a summary with a discussion regarding our experiments and the obtained results.

5.1 Discussion

In this study, similar to previous studies [18], the Knn Algorithm yields the best results in the first experiment. Therefore, only KNN algorithm considered for further investigations. The primary purpose of the first experiment is to see the general distribution of all classes and their success. The most correctly predicted sound among all categories is for the purr sound. The main reason behind the successful identification of the original purr sound is, it is the hardest category to imitate by human voice accordingly to the survey results. When a category is hard to imitate, the imitation quality decrease and the machine can classify easier than the other categories. In the second step, we see what the best approach to detect imitations in terms of categories is. When we gave the classifier all the categories, it performs 94% accuracy. However, when we use only two categories, the accuracy is 91%, which means that as much as the categories are more specific, the accuracy is higher. To be able to compare the experiments, data is sub-sampled for the second experiment to create a balance between the first and the second experiment. The results of 3rd experiment which we have performed to see the relation between discrimination

accuracy and the imitation difficulty are interesting because the growling cat sound is not the easiest category to imitate according to the survey results. However, the accuracy of growling is less than the meow category, which means that classifier is more successful in detecting meow sounds, and the meow sounds are not as realistic as original ones. In table 7, Purr is with the highest accuracy, which also has the most challenging category rating to imitate by participants. Once again, this can be related to the difficulty of the category and imitation qualities and can be further investigated in future studies. Furthermore, When we examine the sounds in different pairs, the classifier has more accuracy identifying purr that might mean harder to imitate.

Figure 17: Experiment 2 Confusion Matrix Test Results for Human and Imitation labels

According to the ranking feature selection technique, Chroma Stft means, and std features were in the five best feature in every method used in Weka. Although this feature is generally used in melodic data, in our case it performs successfully when discriminating the classes. Figure 17 shows this feature's impact on each category. We can see how the distribution is different for PurrCat and PurrHuman classes.

In the 4th experiment, the aim was to see if gender type has an impact on the

vocalization accuracy. However, the results show that the variation is just 1%, and gender does not have an impact on the cat vocalization discrimination. In the 5th experiment, we consider two categories as a cat owner and not a cat owner where the information comes from the survey. The assumption was cat owners can imitate better than comparing to the not cat owners since they are more used to cat sounds and lived together. We saw that the discrimination accuracy does not differ for these group of labels. In the last experiment, we aimed to see the quality of the imitations. To be able to do this, we trained the model with the cat sound vocalizations and tested it on the human imitations. The experiment 6, which we performed to see the quality of the imitations, has Purr as the most successfully predicted category. 58 Purr imitation predicted as Meow and 37 as Growling. In meow, category 90 imitation has been predicted as Growling vice versa 89 growling sound predicted as Meow. The result shows the most confusing categories are Growling and Meow. The accuracy is on the imitation test set is 54%, which is not very good but it provides insights about the imitation data which we created. Even though the Purr category has the most difficult category rating from the users, Purr imitations have more accuracy. Another reason for that might be that Purr category has a different characteristic of the sound which may help discriminated easily than the other sounds. Mouth positions which we mentioned in the beginning also can have an impact on the results. Since the two categories, Meow and Growling, are very similar categories in terms of mouth position. Meow is created when the mouth is open and later closed, Growling is created when the mouth is open, and when it is has a tense position. Considering all experiments, we used Weka's automatic re-sample method to split the data into test and training. This method is works randomly, and one participant has many imitations for each category (approximately 10). For this reason, in the test data, we might have some same participants' imitation, which may have an impact on the results. If we do not split the data as training and test and apply some different techniques, we could have got different accuracy. We intend to have a general idea on imitations, and our aim does not concentrate on having higher accuracy. However, it may be possible to obtain better results with different techniques.

5.2 Conclusions

In this study, first, we analyzed the specific types of cat vocalization, and we came up with three different Cat Vocalization to consider in our research as Meow, Purr, Growling. We use Freesound Cat Sounds to create a data set of these specific type of cat sounds vocalizations. Since Freesound is a collaborative dataset, and everyone is tagging the cat sounds according to their perspective, Freesound Data was leaned and edited for three categories. Then, We created an imitation data set consisting of the vocalizations of the humans precisely for the same categories which we decided as Meow, Purr, Growling. During the collection process of the imitations, we sent a form to participants to compare our discrimination result with the participant segments and to be able to perform different experiment steps. We use Librosa to extract the features of these new data sets and Weka to distinguish cat sounds from their imitations by using machine learning techniques. As a sum of the experiments, we reach the following conclusions; When we train the classifier with cat vocalization sub-categories instead of giving only human and cat labels the accuracy is increasing, imitation difficulty directly proportional to discrimination accuracy, imitations of different gender has a shallow effect on the discrimination accuracy, people who have cats do not tend to do better imitations. Even though the Purr has the most challenging category rating, Purr imitations are the most realistic one to the original cat sounds. In further steps, imitation dataset can be improved, and we can add a different kind of cat sound vocalizations to have a more comprehensive idea on Cat sounds. The most important thing that can be done in the future study is to collect more imitation data and to have only one imitation per person for each sub-category. By this way, imitations which belong to the same person will not exist in the test set. Also, in terms of frequency, these sounds can be investigated further, and a threshold can be decided to determine the categories more accurately. In this study, we intend to have an approach on imitations since exclusively cat sound imitations have not been searched before. Toolboxes we use for our research are chosen from freely available software. All the imitation data resources we use in this thesis are in the following Kaggle profile:

<https://www.kaggle.com/cerencan/cat-imitation-dataset>

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